

FIBRE BRIDGING EFFECT ON DELAMINATION CRACK TIP OPENING DISPLACEMENTS

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SUMMARY: To characterize the behaviour of a delamination, knowledge of the global applied conditions (loads and/or displacements) and the geometry is used to calculate local parameters such as the strain energy release rate G , using Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM). However, due to local perturbations such as fibre bridging, global applied loads are often not transposed directly and uniquely into equivalent local crack tip conditions. Therefore, the objective of this work is to measure the load and displacement applied to a specimen and, at the same time, the crack tip behaviour, when there is an increased resistance with crack growth and fibre bridging, in order to establish a quantitative relation between them. To measure the local strain energy release rate based on the crack opening displacements (*COD*) profiles at a delamination crack tip, an instrumented loading jig designed to fit inside a scanning electron microscope (SEM) has been developed. Mode I loading can be applied to a full size DCB specimen. The applied loads and displacements are measured and slow scan images obtained simultaneously from the SEM are stored. After the test, crack opening displacements (*COD*) are measured on the images to evaluate G_{IL} , the local strain energy release rate, and compared to the global one, G_{IG} , calculated from the globally applied conditions using LEFM. Video images are also recorded to measure G_{IL} just before failure, although with less accuracy. Results are presented for an AS4-3501/6 specimen which was manufactured to promote fibre bridging. This specimen was loaded in mode I until crack growth was observed in the SEM, then immediately partially unloaded. This process was repeated until the crack growth had reached 47 mm. For 5 crack lengths, SEM images were recorded and the *COD* profiles were measured after the test. The results confirm that when fibre bridging is present, G_{IL} is not equal to G_{IG} and, therefore, fibre bridges act by keeping the crack closed. Thus the global applied loads are shielded from the crack tip and a higher load can be applied before crack growth occurs. The more crack growth, the closer the local G_{iCL} is to the initiation toughness G_0 and, therefore, the fibre bridging is affecting the elastic behaviour more than it is dissipating energy.

KEYWORDS: delamination, fibre bridging, crack tip behaviour, crack opening displacement, scanning electron microscope (SEM)

INTRODUCTION

The objective of this work is to study the relationship between the increase in fracture toughness due to fibre bridging and the local crack tip behaviour. Fibre bridging consists of fibres crossing over the crack faces (Figure 1). During the lay-up process, successive layers of fibres preimpregnated with resin are stacked, forming distinct plies. During cure, those plies become more or less intermingled, especially in unidirectional laminates [1]. When a crack grows, the fibres spanning from one layer to the other create a bridge between the two crack surfaces. Moreover, especially in tougher composites, if flaws in planes above or below the crack plane are loaded, the crack can jump to that plane and a bridge is created [1, 2].

Figure 1 Equivalence between the bridged crack and the superposition of an unbridged crack and a crack loaded by pressure at the crack tip faces.

These bridges increase the fracture resistance. Thus the measured critical energy release rate will increase if fibre bridging is created as the crack propagates. The critical energy release rate will not be a unique value: there will be an initiation value G_0 , and then an increase, eventually reaching a stable plateau value if fibre bridges are broken at the same rate as they are created [2].

The quantitative study of the crack tip is made possible by a loading stage designed to fit inside the chamber of Hitachi S-2300 scanning electron microscope (

Figure 2). This permits in-situ quantitative observation of the crack tip while a load is being applied. A complete description of this experimental set-up is available in reference [3]. In a delaminated specimen loaded in opening mode I, the crack faces move apart: this results in a crack opening displacement (COD) profile. Close to the crack tip, the COD profile is a function of r , the distance behind the crack tip and G_{II} , the local strain energy release rate:

$$COD = A_I \sqrt{r} \sqrt{G_{II}} \quad (1)$$

where A_I is a function of the elastic properties of the laminate. The displacements of a gold grid deposited on the specimen prior to loading are measured to provide the COD profile. Therefore, from the COD profile, G_{II} , the local strain energy release rate, can be calculated using Equation 1. Our loading stage is also instrumented to provide measurements of the global applied loads and displacements. Using LEFM, the global strain energy release rate, designated as G_{IG} , is calculated from the global parameters such as applied load or deflection, geometry, crack length and material compliance.

Figure 2 Photograph of the loading jig

The combination of both local and global approaches in this experimental set-up allows us to compare them and establish a relationship. More precisely, we would like to see if the increase in fracture toughness is due to a reduction in the crack driving force or to an increase in the energy consumed in crack propagation, which are the left hand side and right hand side terms in the following local condition for crack growth equation:

$$G_{IL} = G_{IcL} \quad (2)$$

where G_{IL} is the local strain energy release rate obtained from the COD profile and G_{IcL} the local critical strain energy release rate, both for the actual, fibre bridged system. Globally, we also have, at failure:

$$G_{IG} = G_{IcG} \quad (3)$$

where G_{IG} is the global strain energy release rate and G_{IcG} the value of G_{IG} at failure. Consequently, measuring the local COD profile and the global applied conditions permits us to obtain G_{IL} and G_{IG} and therefore the fibre bridging behaviour and its effect on the increase in toughness.

One explanation for the increase in toughness is that the fibre bridges restrain the crack from opening, reducing the crack driving force. Therefore, G_{IL} would be smaller than G_{IG} . Using the superposition principle for the displacements, the bridged crack is equivalent to the unbridged crack minus the crack loaded by distributed pressure on the crack tip faces corresponding to the stresses in the fibre bridges (Figure 1). Therefore,

$$COD_{bridged\ crack} = COD_{unbridged\ crack} - COD_{fibre\ forces} \quad (4)$$

The $COD_{bridged\ crack}$ is the one actually measured and is related to G_{IL} via Equation 1. If the fibre bridges are removed, the crack would open up while the load would remain the same. Thus, using Equation 1, the $COD_{unbridged\ crack}$ is related to G_{IG} . Finally, we define G_{IB} as the strain energy release rate associated with the fibre bridge forces; G_{IB} is related to the $COD_{fibre\ forces}$ using Equation 1. Therefore, we get:

$$\sqrt{G_{IL}} = \sqrt{G_{IG}} - \sqrt{G_{IB}} \quad (5)$$

where G_{IG} is the global strain energy release rate and G_{IB} is the strain energy release rate due to fibre bridging. This stress approach corresponds to an elastic behaviour of the fibre bridges.

An alternative explanation is to consider the work done in creating the fibre bridging. When the energy consumed in crack propagation increases, we obtain from an energy balance,

$$G_{IcL} = G_0 + \Gamma_B \quad (6)$$

where G_0 is the strain energy release rate for the initial crack with no bridging and Γ_B is the energy consumed by fibre bridging breakage and pullout. This energy approach corresponds to a dissipative behaviour of the fibre bridges. If the fibre bridging behaviour is purely elastic, Γ_B is zero and the criterion for crack growth becomes:

$$G_{IL} = G_{IcL} = G_0 \quad (7)$$

and G_{IcL} is constant with crack growth, which means that the COD profile at failure is the same, whatever the crack length. Black squares in Figure 3 represents this behaviour. When the fibre bridging only dissipates energy, G_{IB} is zero and the criterion for crack growth becomes:

$$G_{IL} = G_{IcL} = G_{IG} \quad (8)$$

which is represented by the white squares in Figure 3. A combination of both is possible, and in that case the failure points will fall in between the two bounding cases.

Figure 3 Comparison of G_{IL} and G_{IG} for elastic and dissipative behaviour.

EXPERIMENTAL

It has been shown [4] that a specimen with a higher volume fraction will have a greater increase in resistance to fracture with crack growth because, as the plies are closer together, more fibre bridging occurs. Several methods yield a higher volume fraction material, but the simplest way is to bleed out more resin during the cure by using more bleeder¹ layers [4]. Therefore an AS4-3501/6 specimen with 26 plies manufactured using 15 bleeder plies was used here. The material properties used in the analytical calculations are presented in Table 1. A modified three-point bending test based on ASTM Standard Test Methods for Flexural Properties of Unreinforced and Reinforced Plastics and Electrical Insulating Materials (D790-90) was used to determine simultaneously the Young's and shear moduli. The transverse modulus, E_2 and the Poisson's ratio, ν_{12} , used were the ones obtained from the manufacturer, Hercules Inc. Table 2 presents the specimen characteristics, where h is the half-thickness of the specimen, B the width, L the length and a , the crack length. A 13 mm Teflon insert is embedded at the midplane to create a delamination.

Table 1 Material properties of AS4/3501.

E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	ν_{12}	G_{12} (GPa)
102	9	0.3	7.1

¹ Layer of absorbing material placed around the laminate to absorb any excess resin during processing.

Table 2 Characteristics of specimen.

V_f (%)	Grid spacing (μm)	Insert thickness (μm)	h (mm)	B (mm)	L (mm)	a (mm)
67	25.4	13	1.71	18.86	131.5	19.5 (c ₁) 22.2 (c ₂) 26.7 (c ₃) 35.2 (c ₄) 47.0 (c ₅)

For an orthotropic DCB specimen under mode I load, the expression for the strain energy release rate has been obtained using finite element analysis in conjunction with analytical considerations [5]. With the superposition principle (see Figure 1), G_{IG} is the global energy release rate calculated for the unbridged case (P_I , δ_{IU}) rather than the actual measured case (P_I , δ_I). Since we do not have δ_{IU} , we have calculated G_{IG} for this test using P_I only [5]. As it is calculated from the global values, it is designated as G_{IG} :

$$G_{IG} = \frac{12P_I^2 a^2 (1 + Y_I(\rho)\lambda^{-1/4})^2}{B^2 E h^3} \quad (9)$$

where

$$\lambda = \frac{a_{11}}{a_{22}}, \rho = \frac{a_{12} + \frac{a_{66}}{2}}{\sqrt{a_{11}a_{22}}} \text{ and } Y_I(\rho) = 0.677 + 0.149(\rho - 1) - 0.013(\rho - 1)^2 \quad (10)$$

where a_{ij} are the plane stress elastic compliance constants for the laminate:

$$a_{11} = \frac{1}{E_1}, a_{22} = \frac{1}{E_2}, a_{12} = -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1}, a_{66} = \frac{1}{G_{12}}. \quad (11)$$

Equation 12 is used to evaluate the local values of G_I that gives the best fit to the *COD* profile measured experimentally on the SEM images. This value is called G_{IL} to indicate that it is calculated from the local crack tip conditions.

$$COD = \frac{4}{\sqrt{\pi}} 2^{\frac{1}{4}} \left[\frac{2a_{12} + a_{66}}{2a_{11}} + \sqrt{\frac{a_{22}}{a_{11}}} \right]^{\frac{1}{4}} (a_{11}a_{22})^{\frac{1}{4}} \sqrt{r} \sqrt{G_{IL}} \quad (12)$$

Equation 12 has been derived considering only the first term of the elastic stress singularity, and far from the crack tip, higher order terms will become significant. Note that this first term is a function of $r^{1/2}$, whereas the stress and strain singularities are of the order of $r^{-1/2}$.

The specimen was loaded in mode I until crack growth was observed in the SEM, then immediately partially unloaded. This process was repeated until the crack growth had reached 47 mm. For 5 crack lengths, called c₁ to c₅, slow scan images were recorded, at G_{IG} levels L₁ ($\approx 80 \text{ J/m}^2$), L₂ ($\approx 260 \text{ J/m}^2$) and L₃ ($\approx 400 \text{ J/m}^2$), when possible (see Table 3). After the test, the *COD* profiles were measured from the slow scan images (Figure 4). Video images were also recorded to measure G_{IL} just before failure, with less accuracy.

Table 3 G_{IL} (J/m^2) for the five crack lengths and the three levels of G_{IG} (J/m^2).

Crack length (mm)	G_{ICG} (J/m^2)	$G_{IG} \approx L_1$		$G_{IG} \approx L_2$		$G_{IG} \approx L_3$	
		G_{IG}	G_{IL}	G_{IG}	G_{IL}	G_{IG}	G_{IL}
19.5 (c_1)	105	79	79				
22.2 (c_2)	333	82	70	250	100		
26.7 (c_3)	458	85	85	252	110	380	160
35.2 (c_4)	556	94	70	263	80	400	95
47.0 (c_5)	637	99	55	277	60	426	75

Figure 4 Montage of the SEM crack tip images (crack c_5), for $G_{IG} = 277 J/m^2$.

RESULTS

The R-curve obtained is presented in Figure 5. It can be seen that there is a clear increase of G_{ICG} with crack growth: it increases by a factor of almost 6. The toughness increases very steeply at first, then less so until it reaches a plateau.

Figure 5 Measured R-curve.

The COD profiles for crack lengths c_1 to c_5 are presented in Figure 6 to Figure 10. Each series of dots corresponds to one level of G_{IG} applied. Where there is good agreement between G_{IL} and G_{IG} , the COD profile predicted analytically is plotted as a solid line. Otherwise, the dotted lines represent the same equation, but the value of G_{IL} is adjusted to obtain a better fit to the COD values. Table 3 shows the values of G_{IL} for the different crack lengths and applied, or global, G_{IG} levels.

For the crack length c_1 (Figure 6), which is directly at the Teflon tip, the COD profile is in good agreement with the analytical curve for $G_{IL}=G_{IG}=79 J/m^2$, both in terms of shape and magnitude. All the

load is transmitted to the crack tip, since there is no fibre bridging. This is in agreement with results obtained for specimens with no fibre bridging [3].

Figure 6 Plot of COD vs. r (distance from the crack tip) for crack length c_1 .

Figure 7 Plot of COD vs. r for crack length c_2 .

For c_2 and c_3 (Figure 7 and Figure 8), we can see that at L_1 , G_{IL} is slightly lower G_{IG} . Thus, up to L_1 , almost all the applied load is transmitted to the crack tip. However, as G_{IG} is increased to L_2 and L_3 , we have $G_{IL} \ll G_{IG}$. This means that fibre bridging is restraining the crack tip opening.

For c_4 and c_5 (Figure 9 and Figure 10), the reduction is even greater. First, at L_1 , there is already a significant reduction in G_{IL} . As G_{IG} increases to L_2 and L_3 , G_{IL} is barely increasing. For c_2 , c_4 and c_5 , some fibre bridging is observable directly on the images. A close-up of these fibre bridges has been included on Figure 7, Figure 9 and Figure 10, with an arrow indicating the position of the fibre bridge. The COD profiles invariably show an inflection point right at the position of the fibre bridge: behind it, the COD profiles open up.

Figure 8 Plot of *COD* vs. *r* for crack length c_3 .

Figure 9 Plot of *COD* vs. *r* for crack length c_4 .

Figure 10 Plot of *COD* vs. *r* for crack length c_5 .

The results for the 5 crack lengths are presented as a plot of G_{IL} vs. G_{IG} in Figure 11. G_{ILc} is obtained from video images (failure points, hollow markers) and therefore have less precision, thus error bars showing the standard deviations are included. Since events unfold rapidly at failure, the video images concentrate on one position behind the crack tip of the crack and we do not see if the crack is growing at the crack tip. Therefore, it is difficult to determine the exact moment of failure: the *COD* might be measured on an image where the crack is already growing, and therefore is overestimated. In the present case, we know that this is more likely for the short crack cases (c2 and c3) where the events occurred more rapidly. In particular, G_{ILc} for c₂ might be higher than the real value.

Figure 11 Plot of G_{IL} vs. G_{IG} . Clear marker are obtained from video images and standard deviation is shown as error bar.

As can be seen in Figure 11, for curves c₃, c₄ and c₅, the last points seem to continue the almost linear trend set by the G_{IL}/G_{IG} relationship obtained for lower loads. Moreover, as the crack length increases, the curve is moved downward: the longer the crack length, the lower the G_{IL} at which there is deviation from a $G_{IL}=G_{IG}$ relation and the closer G_{ILc} is to G_0 . Therefore, for longer crack length, failure points are similar to the elastic fibre bridge behaviour illustrated schematically in Figure 3 and the dominant effect is the elastic shielding from the fibre bridges.

Two similar AS4/3501 specimens, but with lower fibre volume fraction, and therefore less increase in toughness with crack growth, were also tested [6]. The resistance curve increase was much less than with the high volume fraction specimen shown here. A difference between G_{IG} and G_{IL} was also noticed, but only for the longest crack length in one specimen. This is not surprising, since there is less increase in toughness and therefore less fibre bridging and the applied G_{IG} levels are not very high. Thus the reduction in G_{IL} was less noticeable.

CONCLUSION

The increase in resistance with crack growth was studied and correlated with the local crack tip behaviour. Up to an applied G_{IG} around 80 J/m^2 , G_{IG} and G_{IL} agree well, for small amounts of crack growth. When G_{IG} is further increased, G_{IL} does not increase as much, and for longer crack growth, it barely increases. This confirms that fibre bridges act by keeping the crack closed. Thus the global applied loads are shielded from the crack tip and a higher load can be applied before crack growth occurs. The longer the crack growth, the closer the local G_{ICL} is to the initiation toughness G_0 and, therefore, the more the effect of fibre bridging is on elastic shielding behaviour rather than dissipation of energy.

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